

Supplementary Materials

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Figure S5. (A, C, E) 2-dimensional, (B, D, F) 3-dimensional interactions of L7, L8 and L9 with DNA-polymerase enzymes of *bacillus subtilis*, respectively.

Figure S6. (A, C, E, G) 2-dimensional, (B, D, F, H) 3-dimensional interactions of L1, L2, L3 and L4 with DNA-polymerase enzymes of *Bacillus subtilis*, respectively.

Figure S7. (A, C, E) 2-dimensional, (B, D, F) 3-dimensional interactions of L7, L8, L9 and COX-2, respectively.

Figure S8. (A, C, E, G) 2-dimensional, (B, D, F, H) 3-dimensional interactions of L1, L2, L3, L4 and L5 with COX-2, respectively.

Table S1: Original file provided in MS Excel as a separate supplementary material

Table S2: Original file provided in MS Excel as a separate supplementary material

Table S3. Nature, distance and energy of interactions of secondary metabolites (L1-L9) with receptor 4TR6.

Ligand	Nature of interaction	Distance (Å⁰)	E (Kcalmol⁻¹)
L1	pi-cation	3.56	-1.9
	pi-H	4.53	-0.6
L2	H-donor	2.97	-3.3
L3	pi-H	4.18	-1.6
	pi-H	4.11	-1.0
L4	H-donor	3.15	-1.6
	H-donor	3.31	-0.8
	H-donor	3.52	-0.8
	H-acceptor	3.15	-3.4
	Ionic	3.98	-0.5
L5	H-donor	2.85	-1.0
	H-acceptor	2.63	-1.1
	pi-cation	4.33	-1.0
L6	H-donor	2.74	-1.9
	H-donor	2.55	-1.2
	H-donor	2.90	-1.7
	H-acceptor	2.95	-1.1
L7	H-donor	3.28	-0.6
	H-donor	2.97	-1.1
	H-acceptor	3.01	-1.0
	pi-H	4.30	-1.1
	pi-H	4.15	-0.7
L8	H-donor	2.89	-1.0
	H-acceptor	2.94	-1.5
	pi-H	4.41	-1.8
L9	H-donor	3.30	-0.9
	H-donor	3.15	-0.9
	H-donor	3.21	-1.1

Table S4. Nature, distance and energy of interactions of secondary metabolites (L1-L9) with receptor 5JVZ.

Ligand	Nature of interaction	Distance (Å⁰)	E (Kcalmol⁻¹)
L1	H-donor	3.11	-1.4
L2	H-acceptor	3.14	-1.9
L3	H-acceptor	3.38	-3.3
	pi-H	4.42	-1.6
	pi-H	4.04	-3.0
L4	H-donor	3.12	-1.4
	H-donor	3.21	-0.9
	H-acceptor	2.99	-0.9
	H-acceptor	3.06	-1.0
	H-acceptor	2.73	-5.1
	ionic	3.92	-0.7
	Ionic	3.95	-0.6
L5	H-pi	5.56	-0.6
	pi-H	4.57	-0.7
	pi-H	4.13	-1.0
L6	H-donor	3.15	-1.3
	H-donor	3.19	-1.3
	H-acceptor	2.65	-1.5
L7	H-donor	3.05	-0.7
	H-donor	2.91	-2.1
	H-acceptor	3.12	-0.6
	pi-H	3.40	-1.0
L8	H-acceptor	3.10	-0.9
	pi-H	3.98	-0.8
L9	H-donor	3.35	-0.8